

Research

Examining Factors in 2015 TIMSS Australian Grade 4 Student Questionnaire Regarding Attitudes Towards Science Using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

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Abstract: *This study is based on the result from student questionnaire about Grade 4 Australian students' attitudes towards science. The respondents for this study are (n=6009) students who responded to TIMSS 2015 student questionnaire and the instrument which is chosen for this study is the set of 26 items with 4-point Likert scale. This study employed exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to examine the possible smallest number of factors which are associated with the attitudes towards science; science lessons, science teachers and learning science. According to the result from exploratory factor analysis, it is suggested that 2 key factors can explain students' attitudes towards science. The two-component solution explained a total of 53.24% of the variance, with Component 1 contributing 41.91% and Component 2 contributing 11.33% respectively. Set of items in factor 1 could be identified and labelled as "Attitudes towards learning science and confidence in science lessons" and those belongs to factor 2 can be labelled as "Attitudes towards science teacher".*

List of terms; *exploratory factor analysis (EFA), students' attitudes, communalities, confidence in science lessons, attitudes towards science teacher.*

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INTRODUCTION

Background Information

TIMSS studies conducted background questionnaire survey for teachers, school principals, curriculum specialists, students and home to explore the conditions of background information about home and school in which students learn, and also students' attitudes towards mathematics

and science. This allows stake holders; the policy makers, teachers and test developers to address the specific concerns and needs in respective context for respective students not only related to their teaching science and science lessons, but also about their attitudes towards science. By examining the student questionnaire about science, it might allow both policy makers and students to identify the underline factors that affect student achievement in science.

Context: Australia

Australia's Year 4 Science Results within International Context

According to the results of TIMSS 2015 science achievement, Australia's 2015 Year 4 science score increased significantly from TIMSS 2011, but as this was a significant decline from TIMSS 2007 the overall change since TIMSS 1995 is not significant (Thomson, Wernert, O'Grady, E & Rodrigues, 2015).

Australian students significantly outperformed students in 17 other countries such as Portugal, New Zealand and France with an average score of 524 score points on the TIMSS Year 4 science scale (Thomson, Wernert, O'Grady, & Rodrigues, 2015). However, they were outperformed by students in 17 other countries, including the United States and England, as well as the participating East Asian countries Singapore, Korea, Japan, Hong Kong and Chinese Taipei (Thomson, Wernert, O'Grady, E & Rodrigues, 2015).

TIMSS 2015 Attitude Questionnaire

TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study) is an international assessment which reveals level of student achievement in mathematics and science, thereby gathering information about the effectiveness of the present school curricula in participating countries (Keser, 2015; Uzun, Butuner & Yigit, 2010). There have been sixth assessments conducted every four years since 1995 and TIMSS 2015 is the sixth assessment in the TIMSS series which has been monitoring 20 years of trends in educational achievement, including comprehensive data on students' contexts for learning mathematics and science.

Statement of the Problem

As TIMSS is the international assessment which has a huge impact on the achievement and progress of students in mathematics and science, it is paramount to explore the background information about the students, home and school situation. Among these, it is worth exploring students' willingness to participate in science activities and confidence in science lessons which can increase motivation. As a result, it is extremely important to develop the set of

questionnaires with possible minimum number of factors which encompass the related items. By exploring the existing data set of TIMSS student questionnaire, there is a possibility of imputing additional significant data which might be useful for collecting information in the next surveys. That is why there is a need to apply exploratory factor analysis to an existing data of 2015 TIMSS student questionnaire regarding Grade 4 Australian students' attitudes towards science.

Purpose of the Study

There has been a lot of studies which have examined the attitudes of students regarding their perceptions about learning science. As a high-stake assessment, TIMSS studies conducted background questionnaire surveys for teachers, students and home to explore the conditions of background information about school and home, and also attitudes of students. Based on the results obtained from these studies, it is possible to estimate students' attitudes towards science, thereby adjusting the instruction and guiding the teachers how to plan the lessons which interest students. It is therefore important to examine the factors that can affect the attitudes of students and which questionnaire items are related to which factors. By examining this, it is possible to develop the questionnaire which can best measure the students' attitudes with high consistency. The purpose of this study is to identify empirically determined the possible smallest number of factors which are associated with the attitudes towards science; science lessons, science teachers and learning science.

Research Questions

This study attempts to answer the following research questions.

1. How many key factors are there in TIMSS 2015 student questionnaire regarding students' attitudes towards science?
2. How can the TIMSS 2015 student questionnaire items regarding students' attitudes towards science be grouped, identified and labelled?

Significance of the Study

This exploratory factor analysis using the secondary data set of student questionnaire of TIMSS 2015 in Australia will help the education stakeholders; policy maker, members of IEA, science teachers and students to determine underlined factors which are associated with the attitudes towards science; science lessons, science teachers and learning science. More specifically, it would be useful for the science teachers to prepare their science lessons to be more interesting, effective and efficient and thus increasing student motivation to learning science. The result

from this study would also help the future researchers to use a model for future quantitative studies to explore the factors or confirm the factors regarding the attitudes towards science.

Limitation of the Study

This study is limited in two ways. The first limitation is that this study only focused on the questionnaire items which focuses on learning science and science lessons which includes only 26 items. Second limitation is that the scope of participant represents only grade 4 students in Australia who participated in TIMSS 2015 science achievement test which means that the results might not represent the other students in other contexts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is a method used to analyze the interdependencies among different observed variables and underpinning theoretical constructs called factors (Jung & Lee, 2011). It aims to uncover the relationship between observed item responses and the hypothesized latent variables called factors as well as the relationship between latent variables (Cai, 2013). The major aim of factor analysis is to identify the possible smallest number of factors which can adequately explain the covariance matrix set of observed variables (Thomson, 2004). In the process of exploratory factor analysis, the initial step is to estimate the parameters of EFA model by extracting the factor loadings which can reproduce the possible observed correlation matrix and maintain the smallest number of factors at the same time (Finch, 2013). One of the approaches to extract factors is the principal component analysis (PCA) which is designed to extract the total variance in the correlation matrix (Finch, 2013). Next step is to transform or rotate the initial factor loadings to make them more meaningful within a single factor which is referred to as a simple structure (Sass & Schmitt, 2010). There are two types of factor rotations namely orthogonal method which assumes factors are not correlated and oblique method in which factors can be assumed as correlated (Finch, 2013). Then, the overall value of a factor solution is measured by looking at the communality value of the individual observed variables which is within the range 0-1 (Finch, 2013). The optimal number of the factor is then determined by looking at the eigenvalues greater than 1 (Guttman, 1958) and the scree plot at which point the plot bends, or flattens out (Cattell, 1996).

TIMSS questionnaire (Science in School)

The 20th anniversary of TIMSS in 2015 established it as the longest standing international education assessment in history (IEA, 2015). The primary goal of TIMSS was assessment of student achievement in STEM disciplines at the fourth/eighth grade levels among international education systems (Reddy, 2005).

There are five broad areas in TIMSS 2015 context questionnaire framework. They are-

1. National and community context;
2. Home context;
3. School context;
4. Classroom context; and
5. Student characteristics and attitudes toward learning.

The TIMSS 2015 International Database contains student achievement data and student, home, teacher, and school background data collected in the 56 countries and 6 benchmarking participants who took part in TIMSS 2015. The 2015 TIMSS study student questionnaire asked students to respond to background information about attitudes toward learning science in schools including 26 items, with 4-point Likert scale of agree a lot to disagree a lot.

Previous Studies Utilizing Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

A number of studies utilize exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to examine the underlying factors related to teachers' attitudes about teaching or students' attitudes towards science. For example, Angelis (2003) conducted exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to examine 13-and 16- year old students' attitudes towards science. Austin (2015) also utilize exploratory factor analysis to explore factors regarding teachers' beliefs, attitudes and perceptions using teacher questionnaire.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design with Sample, Instrument and Analysis

The sample which is chosen for this study is (n=6009) Grade 4 Australian students who participated in 2015 TIMSS science achievement assessment. The instrument used for this study is the set of questionnaires which include 26 items with 4-point Likert scale. The analysis used for this study is the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) which explore or generate the factors by combining two or more variables into single factor or more than one factor in which variables are highly correlated (Jamil, Baharuddin, & Maknu, 2015).

Procedure

To examine the attitudes of Grade 4 students in Australia who took TIMSS science assessment test in 2015, students (n=6009) were asked to respond to 26 items with 4-point Likert scale from the student questionnaire. The preliminary analysis is conducted to analyze the reliability (Cronbach's alpha), to check communalities, KMO and Barlett's test to determine if factor analysis is feasible or not. As an initial step of analysis to assess the feasibility of the test, principal components analysis (PCA) (Finch, 2013) is conducted because the analysis is psychometrically sound and it has already removed the problem of factor indeterminacy which is associated with common factor analysis. For factor rotation and interpretation, orthogonal (uncorrelated) method will be used as it is easier to interpret and report. Finally, the results for communality values, total variance explained and factor loadings will be presented and interpreted.

RESULTS

Demographic Data

The total number of students who responded to questionnaire is (n=6009) with 48.9 % of those being girls and 51.1 of those are boys.

Table 1

Proportion of Students

	Sex of Student	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Girl	2937	48.5	48.9	48.9
	Boy	3072	50.7	51.1	100.0
	Total	6009	99.2	100.0	
Missing	System	48	.8		
Total		6057	100.0		

Table 2

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Adequacy	Measure of Sampling	.966
Bartlett's Test Sphericity	of Appros. Chi-Square df Sig.	80844.914 325 .000

Figure 1. Initial Scree Plot for Questionnaire of Grade 4 Australian Students who Responded to Questionnaire in TIMSS 2015.

Table 3
Rotated Component Matrix

Items	Components		
	1	2	3
I enjoy learning science.	.204	.782	.239
I learn many interesting things in science.	.306	.725	.131
I like science.	.226	.813	.269
I look forward to learning science in school.	.266	.795	.239
Science teaches me how things in the world work.	.338	.585	.039
I like to do science experiments.	.185	.622	.053
Science is one of my favorite subjects.	.192	.740	.253
I know what my teacher expects me to do.	.548	.136	.063
My teacher is easy to understand.	.734	.176	.175
I am interested in what my teacher says.	.682	.422	.131
My teacher gives me interesting things to do.	.680	.404	.123
My teacher has clear answers to my questions.	.766	.172	.125
My teacher is good at explaining science.	.721	.223	.121
My teacher lets me show what I have learned.	.641	.159	.025
My teacher does a variety of things to help us learn.	.737	.249	.094
My teacher tells me how to do better when I make a mistake.	.724	.117	.006
My teacher listens to what I have to say.	.751	.111	.071
I usually do well in science.	.190	.370	.341
I learn things quickly in science.	.269	.376	.311
My teacher tells me I am good at science.	.389	.197	.082
I wish I did not have to study science.	.170	.556	.239
Science is boring.	.183	.618	.131
Science is hard for me than for many of my classmates.	.080	.122	.269
I am just not good at science.	.112	.241	.239

Science is harder for me than any other subject.	.066	.200	.039
Science makes me confused.	.115	.162	.053

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Figure 2. Final Scree Plot for Questionnaire of Grade 4 Australian Students who Responded to Questionnaire in TIMSS 2015.

Table 4
Communalities

Items	Initial	Extraction
SCI\AGREE\ENJOY LEARNING SCIENCE	1.000	.661
SCI\AGREE\LEARN INTERESTING THINGS	1.000	.546
SCI\AGREE\LIKE SCIENCE	1.000	.723
SCI\AGREE\LOOK FORWARD TO LEARN	1.000	.705
SCI\AGREE\SCIENCE TEACHES ME	1.000	.402
SCI\AGREE\SCIENCE EXPERIMENTS	1.000	.323
SCI\AGREE\FAVORITE SUBJECT	1.000	.637
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER EXPECTS TO DO	1.000	.381
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER EASY TO UNDERSTAND	1.000	.571
SCI\AGREE\INTERESTED IN WHAT TCHR SAYS	1.000	.642
SCI\AGREE\INTERESTING THINGS TO DO	1.000	.616
SCI\AGREE\CLEAR ANSWERS	1.000	.603
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER EXPLAINS GOOD	1.000	.572
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER SHOWS LEARNED	1.000	.472
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER DOES A VARIETY	1.000	.581
SCI\AGREE\HOW TO DO BETTER	1.000	.539
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER LISTENS	1.000	.543
SCI\AGREE\USUALLY DO WELL IN SCIENCE	1.000	.469
SCI\AGREE\LEARN QUICKLY IN SCIENCE	1.000	.492

SCI\AGREE\I AM GOOD AT SCIENCE	1.000	.350
ISCI\AGREE\WISH HAVE NOT TO STUDY SCIENCE	1.000	.496
SCI\AGREE\SCIENCE IS BORING	1.000	.566
SCI\AGREE\HARDER FOR ME THAN FOR OTHERS	1.000	.457
SCI\AGREE\JUST NOT GOOD AT SCIENCE	1.000	.532
SCI\AGREE\SCIENCE IS HARDER FOR ME	1.000	.512
SCI\AGREE\SCIENCE MAKES ME CONFUSED	1.000	.449

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 5

Initial Principal Components Analysis Total Variance Explained

Factor	Total Eigenvalues	Percentage variance	of Cumulative Percentage
1	10.897	41.911	41.911
2	2.945	11.326	53.237
3	1.579	6.074	59.311

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Table 6

Final Principal Components Analysis Total Variance Explained.

Factor	Total Eigenvalues	Percentage variance	of Cumulative Percentage
1	10.897	41.911	41.911
2	2.945	11.326	53.237

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Table 7

Rotated Component Matrix after Fixing the Number of Factors

Items	Component	
	1	2
SCI\AGREE\ENJOY LEARNING SCIENCE	.721	.376
SCI\AGREE\LEARN INTERESTING THINGS	.579	.459
SCI\AGREE\LIKE SCIENCE	.754	.392
SCI\AGREE\LOOK FORWARD TO LEARN	.720	.432
SCI\AGREE\SCIENCE TEACHES ME	.421	.475
SCI\AGREE\SCIENCE EXPERIMENTS	.462	.331
SCI\AGREE\FAVORITE SUBJECT	.713	.360
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER EXPECTS TO DO		.597
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER EASY TO UNDERSTAND		.726
SCI\AGREE\INTERESTED IN WHAT TCHR SAYS	.332	.729
SCI\AGREE\INTERESTING THINGS TO DO		.721
SCI\AGREE\CLEAR ANSWERS		.759
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER EXPLAINS GOOD		.730
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER SHOWS LEARNED		.677
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER DOES A VARIETY		.741

SCI\AGREE\HOW TO DO BETTER		.732
SCI\AGREE\TEACHER LISTENS		.733
SCI\AGREE\USUALLY DO WELL IN SCIENCE	.602	.326
SCI\AGREE\LEARN QUICKLY IN SCIENCE	.575	.402
SCI\AGREE\I AM GOOD AT SCIENCE		.517
ISCI\AGREE\WISH HAVE NOT TO STUDY SCIENCE	.680	
SCI\AGREE\SCIENCE IS BORING	.720	
SCI\AGREE\HARDER FOR ME THAN FOR OTHERS	.676	
SCI\AGREE\JUST NOT GOOD AT SCIENCE	.726	
SCI\AGREE\SCIENCE IS HARDER FOR ME	.716	
SCI\AGREE\SCIENCE MAKES ME CONFUSED	.669	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.^a

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

Table 8

Component Transformation Matrix

Component	1	2
1	.709	.706
2	.706	-.709

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Results from Exploratory Factor Analysis

Firstly, to check the suitability of utilizing exploratory factor analysis, this study examines the value of Cronbach's alpha to measure the reliability and the result is 0.94 suggesting that the questionnaire items have relatively internal consistency. According to the result from KMO and Bartlett's test (Table 2), it is found that The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value was 0.966, which exceeds the acceptable value of .60 and the approximate chi-square value of Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is statistically significant, supporting the factorability of the correlation matrix.

Principal component analysis revealed the presence of three components with eigenvalues exceeding 41.91%, 11.33% and 6.07% of the variance respectively (Table 5). As can be seen from a scree plot (Figure 1), a clear break after the third component was found. However, when closely looking at the values of eigenvalues and the percentage of the variance, it is found that the third factor contribute only 6.07 percentage of the variance and the number of items related to that factor is less than 3 and it seems like to be a weak factor. So, it is decided to maintain only two factors which explain 53.24% of the total variance. Then, subsequent factor analysis is conducted and the following results were revealed.

The two-component solution explained a total of 53.24% of the variance, with Component 1 contributing 41.91% and Component 2 contributing 11.33% respectively (Table 6). The Varimax method based on Orthogonal approach was selected. Table 3 shows the result of rotated solution revealing factor loading of each variable and table 4 represents the communalities for extraction of each items.

As can be seen in the table 7, the high value of factor loading for 15 items; 1-7, 18-19 and 21-26 belong to the factor 1, that of items 8 to 17 and 20 belong to the factor 2. In order to label the factors, it could be categorized the first group of items which belong to factor 1 as “Attitudes towards learning science and confidence in science lessons” and those belongs to factor 2 as “Attitudes towards science teacher”.

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATION

The exploratory factor analysis of this study suggests that there are two main key factors which accounts for 53.24% of the total variance. The results from KMO and Bartlett’s test suggest that the factor analysis is suitable for this test. Cronbach’s alpha value is 0.94 and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value was 0.97. The two-component solution explained a total of 53.24% of the variance with about 46 % loss of information, with Component 1 contributing 41.91% and Component 2 contributing 11.33% respectively. Based on the results, there were 15 out of 26 items related to attitudes towards learning science and confidence in science lessons which belong to factor 1 and 11 items related to attitudes towards science teacher. So, it is suggested that the set of questionnaires about student attitudes towards science should be categorized into two main groups by grouping items asking attitudes towards science and confidence in science lessons, and attitudes towards science teacher. Subsequent analysis is recommended to confirm the factors regarding attitudes towards science and it is suggested to use confirmatory factor analysis. For future research, it is advisable to explore the factors for other background questionnaire for home, school and principals in different contexts.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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